

**IMPACT OF TEACHERS' COMMITMENT AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
OF STUDENTS IN SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN PASACAO
DISTRICT, DIVISION OF CAMARINES SUR: AN ANALYSIS**

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Impact of Teachers' Commitment and Academic Performance of Students in Selected Secondary Schools in Pasacao District, Division of Camarines Sur: An Analysis

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Abstract

According to Hoy, Tarter, & Kottkamp (2011), effective teachers need high level of organizational commitment. This suggests that high level of student's achievement requires dedicated teachers who contribute effectively. There is no doubt that high level of student's achievement is strongly related to high level of organizational commitment. The study is anchor on the following educational theories, Social Cognitive Theory of Bandura. Bandura's stresses the importance of observational learning, imitation and modeling. His theory integrates a continuous interaction between behaviors, personal factors- including cognition - and the environment referred to as reciprocal causation model. This study aims to determine the relationship of the teacher's commitment and the academic performance of HS students in the 2nd Congressional District of Milaor toward quality learning of k-12 programs SY 2017-2018. The significance of this study sprung from the importance of enhancing teachers' level of school commitment and the strong intention to develop and improve the students' outcome. The school administrators school principals, teachers and students will benefit from the useful suggestions to ameliorate the teachers' conditions which lead to enhancement of teachers' level of commitment, hence the enhancement of educational level including the students' achievement. The finding of the study will provide a practical significance to serve as a guide to practice framework for understanding teacher's commitments towards their profession and the effects on the students learning. It can possibly contribute to the knowledge concerning school performance and elements that contribute to the student's quality education.

Keywords: *academic achievement or performance, age, commitment, quality education, quality learning*

Introduction

Teaching in general, includes the three major elements: the curriculum, the student, the teacher, and on many secondary issues.

It is believed that the learner is the most important element in the educational process. Celep (2011) stated that in any educational institution, a human being is the most important element because he participates in any position of the input-output process circle of the educational institutions.

According to Hoy, Tarter, & Kottkamp (2011), effective teachers need high level of organizational commitment. This suggests that high level of student's achievement requires dedicated teachers who contribute effectively. There is no doubt that high level of student's achievement is strongly related to high level of organizational commitment.

McNeil et al (2016), stated that commitment has been defined as "the tendency to be involved in positive activities rather than feeling purposeless. In addition, those who are characterized as being 3 committed usually have the ability to set goals for themselves and recognize their own personal value system; On the other hand, good working conditions are very important to elicit their commitment and perform their job properly." They added that the concept of working conditions deals with organizational effectiveness, environment, climate, and ideology.

The school effectiveness has underscored the importance of the personal investment and commitment of teachers to education in general, as well as to the particular mission of their school. Every school has a different "feel" a different "personality." Halpin and Croft (2013) describe this as the organizational climate of a school. The organizational climate of a school is much like the personality characteristics of an individual. He stated that school climate is the relatively enduring quality of a school's environment that is experienced by its members. These characteristics distinguish one school from another and influence the behavior of its members. A healthy school climate consists of combined interaction between members of the school community.

Teaching is not a mission; it is a profession, and like any other, it requires a certain set of knowledge, competencies, skills, and behaviors. As a high school teacher of the K-12 curriculum in the 2nd congressman district of Milaor I would like to zero in on a study one of the dispositions or behaviors-commitment. After all, who or what should a teacher be committed to?

In my case as a public-school teacher, who is not self-employed but rather works for a public educational institution, commitment to this institution should be expected. Abiding by its rules and regulations and embracing its philosophical and pedagogical principles are reasonable requirements.

The greatest commitment of a true educator should be with the STUDENTS and their LEARNING, hence this study.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the relationship of the teacher's commitment and the academic performance of HS students in the 2nd

Congressional District of Milaor toward quality learning of k-12 programs SY 2017-2018. Specifically, this study will answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher relative to:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender/sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. educational attainment; and
 - 1.5. length of service?
2. What is the level of commitment towards teaching of the HS teachers of selected schools in the 2nd District of Camarines Sur?
3. To what extent do teachers show their commitments toward teaching profession, teaching-learning situation and professionalism?
4. What is the academic performance of HS students for the first semester of selected High schools in the 2nd Congressional District of Camarines Sur?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' commitment and the academic performance of the students?
6. What is the implication of the commitment of teacher towards students learning?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational design using survey method was used in this study. A descriptive correlational method refers to a type of study in which information is collected without making any changes to the study subject. This means that the researcher cannot directly interact with the environment in which she is studying in a way that would cause any changes related to the study.

Descriptive research seeks to describe the current status of an identified variable. These research projects are designed to provide systematic information about a phenomenon. The researcher does not usually begin with a hypothesis, but is likely to develop one after collecting data. The analysis and synthesis of the data provide the test of the hypothesis. Systematic collection of information requires careful selection of the units studied and careful measurement of each variable.

According to Best (2013), descriptive method was concerned with the conditions and relationships that exist; practices that prevail; beliefs and processes that were going on; affects that were being felt or trend that was developing. Thus, this method is appropriate for the study which employ recording, analysis, and interpretation of the teacher's commitment towards teaching-learning process and its relationship to the academic performance of the high school students. Correlation, a statistical measure of a relationship between two or more variables, gives an indication of how one variable may predict another. The descriptive techniques discussed above permit a statement, in the form of correlations, about that relationship. However, correlation does not imply causation; that is, simply because two events are in some way correlated (related) does not mean that one necessarily causes the other.

Correlational attempts to determine the extent of a relationship between two or more variables using statistical data. In this type of design, relationships between and among a number of facts are sought and interpreted. This type of research will recognize trends and patterns in data, but it does not go so far in its analysis to prove causes for these observed patterns. Cause and effect are not the basis of this type of observational research. The data, relationships, and distributions of variables are studied only. Variables are not manipulated; they are only identified and are studied as they occur in a natural setting.

Respondents

The subjects of this study were the High School teachers and students in the different high school in the 2nd Congressional District of Camarines Sur, school year 2017-2018.

The following are the High School that participated in this study, teachers' respondents were taken from these schools:

Area 1 San Juan, Libmanan, Camarines Sur which includes the following HS: San Juan National High School, Bahao High School, Carmel High School and Mambayawas High School. Area 2 Pasacao, Camarines Sur includes Pasacao National High School and Tinalmud National High School. Area 3 Milaor, Camarines Sur which include the following Schools: Milaor National High School, San Antonio National High School, Gainza National High School and Dalipay Annex High School.

Instrument

The main instrument of the study was the researcher-made survey questionnaire on the commitment of teacher based on the different reading made. It was administered to the teachers currently teaching in the High School in the District of Camarines Sur., particularly those mentioned in the respondents of the study as to the three areas. The teacher-constructed survey questionnaire was supplemented with unstructured interviews and ocular inspection of the schools. The student performance was taken from the two periodic grading periods of the first semester.

Procedure

After the validation of the instrument, the questionnaires were reprinted to its final form. The researcher secured written permission from the school authorities, principal, school administration and the district supervisor, to allow her to conduct the study. After the approval, the researcher personally administered the survey questionnaire to all the respondent's school and their respective teachers.

The respondents were given enough time to answer the questionnaire. They were collected after a week, while others were return at once. The data collection lasted for two months, from January to March 2018.

Data Analysis

The researcher-made questionnaires were presented to the adviser for review, comments and suggestions. Necessary revisions were integrated based on the suggestions and comments given by the adviser. Final copy was again presented to co-teachers not included as respondents for comments and suggested where solicited and incorporated in the final form of the questionnaire

For the validation of expert, the instruments were presented to the highly reputable validators from the College of Education Department of Laguna State Polytechnic University, and the Graduate School of Laguna State Polytechnic University, ten (10) non-respondents' teachers were used.

After the validation by the expert, the instrument was validated as to its reliability using the test-retest method. The questionnaires undergo the test-test validation using 20 non-respondent teachers of Libmanan Camarines Sur. These teachers were non-respondents. Their participation was on the validation of the instruments.

The instrument was given to the 20 non-respondents HS teachers two time, with and interval of at least 3 weeks. The two tests were check and recorded separately. The relationship between the first and the second test was computed using Pearson product correlation.

The computed Pearson r of 82 indicate a moderately/high relationship between the two tests. This means that the instrument, prepare by the researcher valid and reliable. The instrument can be used for the data collection of the study.

Ethical Considerations

To safeguard the identity of the respondents, the researcher made sure that the name, contact information, and any details of the respondents remained confidential.

Before answering the questionnaire, the researcher explain the objectives, scope and proposed output of the study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data and its interpretation. The data were presented in table form followed by the discussion.

Profile of the Respondents

The demographic profiles of the High School teachers of the District of Camarines Sur are presented in table 1 to 4.

Table 1. Age Distribution of High School Teachers of the District of Camarines Sur

Age Bracket	Area 1		Area 2		Area 3		Total	
	Libmanan Camarines Sur		Pasacao Camarines Sur		Milaor Camarines Sur		<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>		
21-26	4	14.81	9	36	3	14.28	16	21.92
27-30	5	18.51	5	20	8	38.09	18	24.66
31-35	5	18.51	4	16	1	4.76	10	13.69
36-40	7	25.95	3	12	2	9.54	12	16.44
41 and above	6	22.22	4	16	7	33.33	17	23.29
Total	27	100	25	100	21	100	73	100

Table 1 presents the age distribution of high school teachers of the District of Camarines Sur. As presented in the table of the 73 teacher respondents, 18 or 24.66% were on the aged bracket 27 to 30-year-old, 17 or 23.29% on the aged bracket 41years old and above, 16 or 21.92% are on the age bracket 21 to 26v year old,12 or 16.44% on the aged bracket 36 to 40 years old and the 10 or 13.69%-year-old on the aged bracket 31 to 35 years of age. The data imply that there are few teachers who are young or old. Most of the HS teachers were on their mid-twenties and early forties.

Table 2 presents the sex distribution of the High School teachers of the District of Camarines SurCamarines Sur. As shown in the table there were 9or 33.33 % male HS teachers and 18 or 66.66 female. In Milaor there were 7 or 33.33% male teachers and 14 or 66.67% female. While inPasacao, Camarines Sur 9 or 36% male and 16 or 64%female.

Generally, as shown in the table there were more female than male teachers 48 of 65.75% against 25 or 34.25%. This is because the teaching profession is dominated by female teachers. Teaching is not prestige jobs, that's makes it predominantly by female. Even though there is no relation between gender and student's achievement, the more balance gender balanced teachers (men and women)

are also good for children development, including in primary school. In addition, there is a 'myth' that said only women can be a good teacher. (Adhimas Wijaya, 2014).

Table 2. Sex Distribution of High School Teachers of the District of Camarines Sur

Sex	Area 1		Area 2		Area 3		Total	
	Libmanan Camarines Sur		Pasacao Camarines Sur		Milaor Camarines Sur		f	%
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Male	9	33.33	9	36.00	7	33.33	25	34.25
Female	18	66.66	16	64.00	14	66.67	48	65.75
Total	27	100	25	100	21	100	73	100

Table 3 presents the civil status of high school teachers of the District of Camarines Sur. As presented in the table of the 73 HS teachers 46 or 63.02 % were married while 27 or 36.98% were single.

Table 3. Civil status of High School Teachers of the District of Camarines Sur

Civil Status	Area 1		Area 2		Area 3		Total	
	Libmanan Camarines Sur		Pasacao Camarines Sur		Milaor Camarines Sur		f	%
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Single	8	29.63	12	48.00	7	33.33	27	36.98
Married	19	70.37	13	52.00	14	66.67	46	63.02
Total	27	100	25	100	21	100	73	100

Specifically, the HS teachers of CanderiaCamarines Sur, 19 or 70.37% were married while 8 or 29.63% were single. On the other hand, there were almost the same number of single and married teacher with 12 or 48% single and 13 or 52% married teachers ofPasacao, Camarines Sur. While half of the HS teachers in Milaor Where single, 7 or 33.33% and 14 or 66.67 were married.

Table 4. Educational Attainment of the High School teachers of Camarines Sur

Educational Attainment	Area 1		Area 2		Area 3		Total	
	Libmanan		Pasacao		Malaor		f	%
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Bachelor Degree	4	14.81	2	12.00	6	28.57	12	16.44
BS w/ Masteral Units	12	44.44	14	56.00	10	47.61	36	49.31
Master's Degree Holder	8	29.64	5	20.00	5	23.82	18	24.66
MA w/ Ph D/Ed D Units	3	11.11	2	8.00	0	0	5	6.85
Ph D/Ed D Degree Holder	0	0	2	8.00	0	0	2	2.74
Total	27	100	25	100	21	100	73	100

The Educational Attainment of the High School teachers of Camarines Sur is presented in table 4. As shown in the table only two teachers were holder of doctorate degree this is 2.74% of the total respondents. These teachers are among the 25 teachers of Pasacao, Camarines Sur. Five teachers or 6.85% were in the process of completing their doctorate degree. Three of which were teachers of different HS in Libmanan Camarines Sur and two from Pasacao, Camarines Sur. 18 teachers of 24.665 have% finished mastered degree of which 8 were teachers of HS in Libmanan, five each were HS teachers of Pasacao and Milaor Camarines Sur. 36teachers or 49.31% were holder of Bachelor degree and with units in Master's degree of which 14 teachers come from Pasacao, 12 teachers from Libmanan and 10 teachers from Milaor Camarines Sur. 12 teachers or 16.44 were holders of bachelor degree. Of these 12 teachers 6 come from Milaor, four teachers from Libmanan, and two teachers from Pasacao, Camarines Sur.

Table 5. Year of Experience of the High School teachers of Camarines Sur

Years of Experience	Area 1		Area 2		Area 3		Total	
	Libmanan		Pasacao		Milaor		f	%
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Below	7	25.93	5	20.00	1	4.76	13	17.80
11-5	6	22.22	4	16.00	2	9.52	12	16.33
6-10	4	14.81	6	24.00	4	19.00	14	19.17
11-15	3	11.11	3	12.00	4	19.00	10	13.70
15 and above	7	25.93	2	8.00	10	47.62	19	26.30
Total	27	100	25	100	21	100	73	100

Table 5 show the years of experience of the HS teachers. As presented in the table 19 or 26.30% have 15 and above in teaching years, seven were teaching in Libmanan, 10 in Milaor and 2 teachers inPasacao, Camarines Sur. 14 or 19.17% teachers with 6 to 10 years' experience of which 6 fromPasacao, and 4each from Libmanan and MilaorCamarines Sur. Twelve or 16.33% teachers with1 to5 years teaching experience, 6 teachers teach in Libmanan, four fromPasacao and 2 from MilaorCamarines Sur.

On the other hand, there were 13 teachers or 17.80% with less than a year of experience of which 7 teachers teaches at different HS in Libmanan, five (5) teachers fromPasacao and one (1) teacher from MilaorCamarines Sur.

The data indicates that the HS teachers were experience teachers as shown by their numbers of years in the field of teaching.

Table 6. *The Subject Taught by the HS Teachers*

Subject Taught	Area 1		Area 2		Area 3		Total	
	Libmanan		Pasacao		Milaor		f	%
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Languages	6	22.22	7	28.00	4	19.04	17	23.29
Sciences	2	7.41	2	8.00	4	19.04	8	10.96
Mathematics	6	22.22	4	16.00	4	19.04	14	19.18
Tech-Voc	7	25.93	6	24.00	5	23.81	18	24.65
Values Ed	2	7.41	2	8.00	1	4.76	5	6.85
Elective	1	3.70	2	8.00	2	9.52	5	6.85
MAPEH	3	11.11	2	8.00	1	4.76	6	8.22

The subject taught by the teachers was presented in table 6. As shown in the table, the highest number of teachers taught the Technical and Vocational

Subjects, there were 18 teachers or 24.65% where 7 teachers from different HS in Libmanan, 6 teachers fromPasacao and 5 teachers from Milaor. This is followed by languages teachers (English and Filipino) with 17 teachers or 23.29% of which six (6) teachers comes from Libmanan, seven (7) teachers fromPasacao and four (4) teachers from different HS of MilaorCamarines Sur.

The third in rank is mathematics teachers with 14 teachers or 19.18%, wherein six (6) teachers came from different HS of Libmanan and four (4) teachers each from Pasacao and Milaor Camarines Sur. While there were eight (8) science teachers or 10.96% of which four (4) teachers came from different HS in Milaor, and two (2) teachers each from Libmanan and Pasacao, Camarines Sur. There were six (6) MAPEH teachers or 8.22%, three (3) of the teachers came from different HS in Libmanan, two (2) teachers from Pasacao and one (1) teacher from Milaor Camarines Sur. Five (5) teachers or 6.85%, taught Values Education wherein two (2) teachers each came from Libmanan and Pasacao, and one (1) from Milaor Camarines Sur. The remaining five (5) teachers or 6.85% taught elective subject, one (1) teacher from Libmanan and two (2) teachers each from Pasacao and Milaor Camarines Sur.

The data indicates that there were more teachers in the field of technical-vocational courses, languages, mathematics and Science.

Performance of HS students for the first semester

Table 7. *Academic Performance of the High School Students for the First Grading*

Sex	Area 1		Area 2		Area 3		Total	
	Libmanan		Pasacao		Milaor		F	%
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Excellent (100-94).	23	6.05	21	6.0	20	5.88	64	5.98
Every Satisfactory (93-88)	102	26.84	108	30.85	97	28.52	307	28.69
Satisfactory (87-82)	177	46.57	157	44.85	167	49.11	501	46.82
Needs Improvements (81-75)	68	17.89	57	16.28	48	14.11	173	16.17
Failed (74 and below)	10	2.63	7	2.0	8	2.35	25	2.33
Total	380	100	350	350	340	340	1070	100

Table 7 on the next page, presents the academic performance of the high school students for the first grading period. As presented in the table 64students or 5.98% have an excellent performance with point grade average of 100to 94, wherein 23 students came from Libmanan, 21 students fromPasacao and 20 students from Milaor. On the other hand, 25 students or 2.33% failed, with point grade average of 74 and below, of which 10 students from Libmanan, 7students from Pasacao and 8 students from MilaorCamarines Sur.

On the other hand, there were 307 students or 28,68% with very Satisfactory performance having point grade average of 93 to 88. These includes 102 students from Libmanan, 108 students from Pasacao and 97 students from MilaorCamarines Sur.

There were 501 students who obtained a satisfactory performance with a point grade average of 87 to 82, of these 177 students come from Libmanan, 157students fromPasacao, Camarines Sur and 167 students from MilaorCamarines Sur.

One hundred seventy-three (173) students or 16.17% need improvement. Their point grade average is 84 to 75. These includes 68 students from Libmanan,57 students fromPasacao and 48 students from MilaorCamarines Sur. As shown by the data the academic performance of the students was normally distributed. Most of them have an average performance. There are some students that must be giving more attention. Since the data is on the first grading period, given more time and encouragement to these students, their performance can still improve.

The HS teachers' commitments were group into three categories: 1. Commitment towards work or the Teaching Profession; 2. Commitment towards students teaching and learning; and Commitment towards her/his profession.

Table 8 present the HS Teachers Commitment towards work. As presented in the table the HS teacher of Libmanan,Pasacao and Milaor indicated they always do or practice the following statement: likes working with young people, and takes an interest in knowledge and

ideas; his/her students lack of knowledge and skills is not an excuse to decrease his/her feeling of compassion for them;; Endeavors to establish and maintain a learning environment where students can learn from their mistakes; Manage students' behavior highly effectively with clear rules that are consistently enforced; Creates a positive atmosphere in the classroom through excellent relationship; and Incorporates high levels of praise and enthusiasm. These statements obtained a weighted mean ranging from 4 to 3.25 with a description of "Always Practice".

Table 8. *Teachers Commitment towards work or the Teaching Profession*

<i>Commitment towards work or the Teaching Profession</i>	<i>Area 1</i>		<i>Area 2</i>		<i>Area 3</i>	
	<i>Libmanan</i>		<i>Pasacao</i>		<i>Milaor</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>D</i>
1. Likes working with young people, and takes an interest in knowledge and ideas	3.74	A	3.84	A	3.90	A
2. Students lack of knowledge and skills cannot be an excuse to decrease his/her feeling of compassion for them.	3.74	A	3.68	A	3.76	A
3. Aware of world issues, and current events in the classroom and effectively reflects them in his/her works at school	3.70	A	3.12	O	3.02	O
4. Tolerates absurd and meaningless things that students exhibit in their behaviors but at the same time critical and very attentive to manners that students must have.	3.12	O	3.02	O	3.02	O
5. Avoids condemning ideas of unpopular and young people and attempts to create a culture of mutual respect.	3.14	O	3.00	O	3.06	O
6. Endeavors to establish and maintain a learning environment where students can learn from their mistakes.	3.85	A	3.64	A	3.76	A
7. Takes his missions seriously and reflects his ideas and beliefs clearly.	3.05	O	3.64	A	3.76	A
8. Dedicated to the learning of pupils	3.81	A	3.88	A	3.81	A
9. Maintains high levels of student engagement	3.12	O	3.68	A	3.71	A
10. Manage students' behavior highly effectively with clear rules that are consistently enforced.	3.81	A	3.72	A	3.81	A
11. Creates a positive atmosphere in the classroom through excellent relationship;	3.81	A	3.84	A	3.71	A
12. Incorporates high levels of praise and enthusiasm.	3.70	A	3.76	A	3.71	A
Total	3.59	A	3.59		3.58	

Legend: 4.00-3.25, Always (A); 3.24-2.50, Often (O); 2.49-1.75, Seldom (S); 1.74-1.00, Never (N)

HS teachers Often times tolerates absurd and meaningless things that students exhibit in their behaviors but at the same time critical and very attentive to manners that students must have and avoids condemning ideas of unpopular and young people and attempts to create a culture of mutual respect. These statements obtained a weighted mean ranging from 3.34 to 2.5. They have different perception on the awareness of world issues, and current events in the classroom and effectively reflects them in his/her works at school; takes his missions seriously and reflects his ideas and beliefs clearly and maintains high levels of student engagement. The HS of Libmanan always practice them, while the HS of Pasacao and Milaor, often time practice them. Libmanan teachers' commitment earned a mean of 3.59, Pasacao teacher's commitment with a mean of 3.59 and Milaor teachers' commitment with a mean 3.58. These indicate that teachers of the district of Camarines Sur were always committed to their work or profession.

Table 9. *Teachers Commitment towards students teaching and learning*

<i>Commitment toward students teaching and learning</i>	<i>Area 1</i>		<i>Area 2</i>		<i>Area 3</i>	
	<i>Libmanan</i>		<i>Pasacao</i>		<i>Milaor</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>D</i>
1. Choose materials that meet the learners' needs, not theirs.	3.70	A	3.68	A	3.86	A
2. Plan the lesson with the learners in mind, taking into account their specific interests, dispositions and difficulties.	3.67	A	3.56	A	3.90	A
3. Make an effort to mark students' exercises/assessments on time so as to provide immediate feedback and minimize their anxiety.	3.70	A	3.40	A	3.57	A
4. Make it a point to know all the students' names as early as possible in the term.	3.48	A	3.48	A	3.76	A
5. Pay attention to their students and notice when something is wrong, or when they've had a haircut, for example.	3.55	A	3.56	A	3.57	A
6. Feel rewarded by students' successes and frustrated by their failures, and in the latter case, they reflect upon what they could have done differently to prevent such failures.	3.67	A	3.72	A	3.76	A
7. Never see even the most disturbing and difficult students as enemies.	3.59	A	3.36	A	3.67	A
8. Understand that disturb student's behaviors may stem from difficulties in other dimensions of these students' lives and feel stimulated to help.	3.55	A	3.32	A	3.71	A
9. Want their students to be successful in their use of the learning materials and want to help them become more autonomous learners.	3.63	A	3.76	A	3.81	A
10. Provide opportunities for students to keep in touch with them	3.63	A	3.36	A	3.81	A
11. Believe that everyone can learn and provide conditions for this to happen, including individualized attention.	3.70	A	3.68	A	3.91	A
12. Try hard not to allow their personal problems or needs affect their classes.	3.55	A	3.56	A	3.62	A
Total		100	3.54	100	73	100

Legend: 4.00-3.25, Always (A); 3.24-2.50, Often (O); 2.49-1.75, Seldom (S); 1.74-1.00, Never (N)

Table 9 present the HS teachers commitment towards students teaching and learning. A presented in the table the teachers indicated that they “Always” practice the following teaching learning situation statements: Choose materials that meet the learners’ needs, not theirs; plan the lesson with the learners in mind,taking into account their specific interests, dispositions and difficulties; make an effort to mark students' exercises/assessments on time so as to provide immediate feedback and minimize their anxiety; make it a point to know all the students ‘names as early as possible in the term; Pay attention to their students and notice when something is wrong; feel rewarded by students' successes and frustrated by their failures, and in the latter case, they reflect upon what they could have done differently to prevent such failures; never see even the most disturbing and difficult students as enemies; understand that disturb students behaviors may stem from difficulties in other dimensions of these students' lives and feel stimulated to help; want their students to be successful in their use of the learning materials and want to help them become more autonomous learners; provide opportunities for students to keep in touch with them; believe that everyone can learn and provide conditions for this to happen, including individualized attention; and try hard not to allow their personal problems. These statements obtained a weighted mean ranging from 4 to 3.25 with a description of "Always Practice"

Table 10. *Teachers Commitment towards Professionalism*

<i>Professionalism</i>	<i>Area 1</i>		<i>Area 2</i>		<i>Area 3</i>	
	<i>Libmanan</i>		<i>Pasacao</i>		<i>Milaor</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>D</i>
1. Through knowledge of the subject	3.63	A	3.72	A	3.90	A
2. Through knowledge of the teaching and learning process including being up to date with relevant outcomes of educational research).	3.59	A	3.72	A	3.76	A
3. Knowledge of policy and organization in education	3.48	A	3.72	A	3.62	A
4. Able to conduct research within the practice of schools	3.18	O	3.04	O	3.22	O
5. Able to contribute to collaborative learning of professional communities	3.48	A	3.60	A	3.76	A
6. Committed to the profession and the collective group of professionals	3.59	A	3.64	A	3.76	A
7. Committed to the ethical code of the profession and the integrity of his/her work	3.67	A	3.76	A	3.76	A
8. Focused on continuous professional development	3.67	A	3.72	A	3.81	A
9. Focus on improvement and innovation of teaching	3.67	A	3.64	A	3.71	A
10.Collaboration with colleagues and stakeholders;	3.59	A	3.60	A	3.81	A
11.Involvement in the innovation of the profession;	3.55	A	3.68	A	3.71	A
12.Develops well planned, prepared and paced lessons that maintain high levels of interaction with the class	3.63	A	3.52	A	3.71	A

Legend: 4.00-3.25, Always (A); 3.24-2.50, Often (O); 2.49-1.75, Seldom (S); 1.74-1.00, Never (N)

Table 10 show the HS teacher responses on their commitment towards professionalism. As presented in the table, the teachers "always" perform/do the following statement: having through knowledge of the subject; through knowledge of the teaching and learning process including being up to date with relevant outcomes of educational research); knowledge of policy and organization in education; able to contribute to collaborative learning of professional communities; committed to the profession and the collective group of professionals; committed to the ethical code of the profession and the integrity of his/her work; focused on continuous professional development; focus on improvement and innovation of teaching; collaboration with colleagues and stakeholders; involvement in the innovation of the profession; and develops well planned, prepared and paced lessons that maintain high levels of interaction with the class. These statements obtained a weighted mean ranging from 4 to 3.25 with a description of “Always Practice.

On the statement, Able to conduct research within the practice of schools they indicated that they often time practice this area according to their field of specialization. The process of doing research needed time and effort. Most of the teacher do the action research. This is required by the Department of Education at the end of the school year.

Relationship between the teachers' commitment and academic performance of the students

On the result with respect to the null hypotheses: "There is no significant relation at (a= 0.05) between HS teachers' commitment and their students ‘academic performance.

The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between teachers ‘commitment and students' academic achievement. Table 11shows the results.

Table 11. *Pearson Correlation Coefficient of the Relation Between Teachers’ Commitment and Students' Achievement*

<i>Teachers' commitment</i>		<i>Students' achievement</i>		<i>Correlation</i>
<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	
3.63	0.41	75.60	9.60	0.81*

* Significant at(α=0.05)

Table 11 indicates that there is a significant positive relation between teachers' commitment and students' academic achievement. The table showed that the Pearson Correlation Coefficientwas significant between teachers ‘commitment and students' academic achievement which turned out to be "r=0.81". That is, HS teachers are committed people. It can be concluded from these results that

committed teachers lead to a higher level of their students' academic achievement. The researcher also attributed this result to the faithfulness and honesty in teaching that motivate and encourage students to be more attentive, active, well disciplined, and have a better spirit of competition, hence attain higher grades. All these positive qualities encourage their teachers to be more committed. But this doesn't mean that commitment was the only factor that affects students' academic achievement.

The significant results of this study are similar to those of Martinez and Maynard (2012); who concluded that there was a strong relationship between teachers' commitment and students' academic achievement.

Conclusions

Based on the finding of the study, the HS teachers of Camarines Sur were educationally qualified for their profession. They are physically, chronologically and mentally fit for the job.

The academic performances of the students were normally distributed. Most of them have an average performance. There are some students that must be giving more attention particularly those who failed and who's that needed improvement. Since the data is on the first and 2nd grading period, given more time and encouragement to this student, their performance can still improve.

Develop ways and mean to inculcating Teacher Commitment

The High Schools administration should maintain and enhance a comfortable instructional environment for the teachers which has a democratic climate, good salary, and less written work.

School principals/administrators in the High School should be more flexible and give their teachers more freedom, involve them in the school activities, and engage them in the process of decision making.

The HS teachers of the 2nd district is already committed in their profession. They should be rewarded in order to reinforce and motivate them, hence increase their commitment to their occupation. Inspire new teachers to be committed also

Supervisors, and experienced teachers should be helpers, supporters and guides to make novice teachers feel comfortable; hence to indicate their problems frankly and motivates them to be committed. They should be the role model for the novice.

Further research is needed to compare HS teachers or Junior and elementary teachers' commitment using a larger sample than the current one.

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